

A Study on Financing of Agriculture by Banks in India with Special Reference to Bank of India and State Bank of India

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Abstract:

The present study is descriptive and factual in nature and aims to assess the different types of agricultural loans available to farmers in India. Agriculture has historically been the backbone of the Indian economy, contributing significantly to employment and Gross Domestic Product (GDP). However, the sector faces numerous challenges such as uncertain climatic conditions, fluctuating market prices, and rising input costs, which make access to institutional finance essential (Mohanty et al., 2021).

The study concludes that Indian banks, particularly Bank of India and State Bank of India, offer a wide range of agricultural loan schemes tailored to the needs of farmers, Farmer Producer Organizations (FPOs), and agribusinesses. These schemes aim to promote productivity, sustainability, and financial inclusion in the agricultural sector.

Keywords: Agricultural Finance, Pledge, Farmer Producer Organization (FPO)

Introduction:

Agricultural finance plays a crucial role in the development of the farming sector in India. Selected Indian banks adopt a multi-modal approach to agricultural financing that considers the diverse needs of farmers across regions and farming practices. These banks are instrumental in increasing credit penetration, promoting technological adoption, and supporting sustainable agricultural practices.

The core of agricultural finance lies in providing farmers with timely credit to meet their input requirements. Indian banks offer various loan products to support the purchase of seeds, fertilizers, pesticides, irrigation facilities, and farm machinery. These loans are generally provided on concessional terms with flexible repayment schedules, keeping in mind the seasonal and cyclical nature of agricultural activities.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To study the concept of agricultural finance
2. To assess different types of loans available to farmers

3. To analyze agricultural loan facilities of Bank of India
4. To analyze agricultural loan facilities of State Bank of India

Review of Literature:

Murray (1953) defined agricultural finance as “an economic study of borrowing funds by farmers; of the organisation and operation of farm lending agencies, and of society’s interest in credit for agriculture.”

Tandon and Dhondyal (1962) described agricultural finance as a branch of agricultural economics dealing with the provision and management of banking services and financial resources related to individual farm units.

Research Methodology:

The study is based on secondary data collected from official websites, annual reports, and published documents of **Bank of India** and **State Bank of India**.

**Agricultural Loan Schemes of Bank of India:
STAR Farmer Producer Organisations (SFPOs)
Scheme:**

The scheme focuses on financing Farmer Producer Organizations (FPOs) and Farmer Producer Companies (FPCs) to strengthen agri-value chains.

Eligibility:

Registered Farmer Producer Companies fulfilling eligibility criteria under Section IX-A of the Indian Companies Act, 1956 and incorporated with the Registrar of Companies (RoC).

Quantum of Finance:

- **Term Loan:** Based on project cost with a margin of 15%
- **Working Capital:** Based on cash flow analysis

Purpose of Loan:

- Purchase of agricultural inputs
- Warehouse receipt financing
- Marketing and distribution activities
- Setting up Common Service Centres
- Food processing units
- Common irrigation facilities
- Custom hiring of farm machinery
- Purchase of high-tech farming equipment
- Solar plants and agricultural infrastructure
- Animal husbandry infrastructure
- Financing agri-value chains

Features

- Attractive interest rates
- Simple application procedure
- Credit guarantee available through NABSanrakshan

TAT:

Upto Rs.10.00 lakh	Above Rs 10 lakhs to Rs.5.00 crore	Above Rs.5 Crores
7 business days	14 business days	30 business days

Star Krishi Urja Scheme:

A Central Sector Scheme under Pradhan Mantri Kisan Urja Suraksha Evam Utthan Mahabhiyan (PM KUSUM)

Features:

- No security for loans upto Rs 2.00 lakh.
- The beneficiaries will be eligible for 60% subsidy under the scheme for Component A (Small solar power plant) and Component B (Standalone power pumps). The subsidy will be shared by Central Government (30%) and State Government (30%).

TAT:

Upto Rs.10.00 lakh	Above Rs 10 lakhs to Rs.5.00 crore	Above Rs.5 Crores
7 business days	14 business days	30 business days

Purpose:

- Setting Up of Decentralized Ground/ Stilt Mounted Grid Connected Solar or Other Renewable Energy Based Power Plants
- Installation Of Stand-Alone Solar Pumps and Solarisation of Grid Connected Pumps.

Eligibility:

Farmers/ Group of Farmers/ Co-Operatives/ Farmer Producer Organisations (FPO)/ Water User Associations (WUA)/ Proprietors/ Partners/ Llps/ Companies, Etc.

Star Bio Energy Scheme (Sbes):

To Promote Setting Up Of Projects For Recovery Of Energy In The Form Of Biogas/ Bio-CNG From Urban, Industrial And Agricultural Waste Under SATAT(Sustainable Alternative Towards Affordable Transportation) Initiative Promoted By Ministry Of Petroleum And Natural Gas

Features:

Fund Based And Non Fund Based Facilities Available Finance For Both WC Requirement And Setting Up Unit Available. Central Financial Assistance Of Rs.4.0 Crore Per 4800 Kgs Of Biocng/Day Generated From 12000m3 Biogas/ Day Mega Watt Equivalent ((Mweq). (Maximum CFA-Rs.10 Crore/ Project) Available From Ministry Of New And Renewable Energy (MNRE).

TAT:

Upto Rs.10.00 lakh	Above Rs 10 lakhs to Rs.5.00 crore	Above Rs.5 Crores
7 business days	14 business days	30 business days

Purpose:

For financing to Compressed Bio Gas projects

Quantum of finance:

Need based finance available.

Eligibility:

Entrepreneurs, who have been awarded Letter of Intent (LoI) by Oil Marketing Companies (OMCs) for supply of CBG under SATAT Scheme. Obtention of LoI from OMCs is a pre-condition for processing the loan

Finance Against Pledge Of Warehouse Receipts (WHR):

Scheme for Financing against pledge of Electronic Negotiable Warehouse (e-NWR)/ Negotiable Warehouse Receipts (NWR)

Purpose:

For Financing against pledge of Electronic Negotiable Warehouse (e-NWR)/ Negotiable Warehouse Receipts (NWR) issued by-

- Repositories (approved by WDRA) for stocks/goods stored in WDRA accredited Warehouses/Cold Storages or EWR issued by accredited Warehouses/Cold Storages
- Central Ware house Corporation (CWC) or State Ware house Corporation (SWC).

Quantum Of Finance:

Finance upto Rs.75 lacs available for accredited Cold Storge, warehouses

Features:

30% of the market value of the farm produce or value mentioned in e-NWR/NWR, whichever is lower (For WDRA accredited Cold Storge, warehouses)

Eligibility:

Individual farmers (owner/tenant farmer & Share cropper), FPO/ FPC and JLG engaged in production activities, group of farmers engaged in production of crops. Farmers enjoying KCC facility as well as non-borrower farmers are eligible.

Security:

Warehouse receipts to be pledged

Types of SBI Agriculture Loans:

SBI provides several loan schemes to cater to different agricultural needs:

Kisan Credit Card (KCC)/Crop Loan: This provides timely and sufficient short-term credit for cultivation expenses, post-harvest activities, and farm maintenance.

Interest Rate: For loans up to ₹3 lakh, the interest rate is 7% per annum, with an additional 3% interest subvention for prompt repayment, bringing the effective rate to 4% p.a...

Security: Collateral is waived for KCC limits up to ₹2 lakh (or ₹3 lakh under tie-up arrangements).

Farm Mechanization Loans: These loans finance the purchase of essential farm machinery.

Tractor Loan: For purchasing tractors and accessories. Eligibility often requires a minimum land holding and a credit score above 650.

Financing of Combine Harvester/Pumpset:

Specific loans for other major equipment and irrigation systems.

Agriculture Gold Loan:

Farmers can pledge gold ornaments to avail loans for various agricultural purposes at attractive interest rates.

Kisan Samriddhi Rin/Agriculture Cash Credit:

For progressive farmers, agri-companies, and large farmers needing cash credit for end-to-end farming.

Loans for Allied Activities:

Financing is available for allied activities such as dairy, poultry, fisheries, and piggeries.

Asset Backed Agri Loan:

A term loan for a wide range of traditional, modern, and high-tech farm activities, with a maximum loan of up to ₹50 lakhs.

Government Sponsored Schemes:

SBI also facilitates various government initiatives like the PM-KUSUM Scheme (for solar power in agriculture) and the Agriculture Infrastructure Fund (AIF).

Eligibility and Documentation**Eligibility:**

Generally open to individual farmers, joint borrowers, tenant farmers, sharecroppers, Self-Help Groups (SHGs), and Farmer Producer Companies (FPCs). Some schemes may require a minimum landholding. A CIBIL score above 650 is typically required for larger loans, though a lack of credit history may also be acceptable.

Documents:

- Duly filled and signed application form with passport-size photographs.
- Identity proof (Aadhar Card, Voter ID, PAN Card, Passport, Driving License).
- Address proof (Aadhar Card, Voter ID, Driving License, electricity bills).
- Proof of landholding/cultivation duly certified by revenue authorities.

How to Apply:

You can apply for an SBI agriculture loan through the bank's official website or by visiting your nearest branch. The bank provides an [online](#)

[application portal](#) and a range of loan application forms on its website.

Conclusion:

Agriculture remains the backbone of the Indian economy, and the availability of timely and adequate institutional finance is crucial for its sustainable growth. This study highlights the significant role played by commercial banks, particularly Bank of India and State Bank of India, in meeting the diverse financial needs of farmers, Farmer Producer Organizations (FPOs), and agribusiness enterprises.

The analysis reveals that both banks offer a wide range of agricultural loan products, covering crop production, farm mechanization, allied activities, renewable energy projects, bio-energy initiatives, and post-harvest financing through warehouse receipt-based loans. Schemes such as Kisan Credit Card, STAR Farmer Producer Organisation Scheme, Bio-Energy financing, PM-KUSUM, and finance against warehouse receipts demonstrate the banks' commitment to promoting productivity, modernization, and income stability in the agricultural sector.

Furthermore, flexible repayment schedules, concessional interest rates, government interest subvention, and credit guarantee support have enhanced farmers' access to formal credit. These initiatives not only reduce dependence on informal sources of finance but also encourage adoption of advanced technologies and sustainable farming practices.

In conclusion, Bank of India and State Bank of India play a vital role in strengthening agricultural finance in India. Continued expansion of credit outreach, simplification of loan procedures, and increased awareness among farmers will further improve the effectiveness of agricultural financing and contribute to inclusive rural development and long-term economic growth.